

**STAFF WELFARE PACKAGES AND PERFORMANCE OF ENUGU
ELECTRICITY DISTRIBUTION COMPANY (EEDC), IN ENUGU STATE,
NIGERIA**

Nnamani Jane Udewo, Ugwu, Felix Ikechukwu Ph.D and Oluka Kingsley Ugochukwu

*Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences

Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8249570>

Abstract: The study evaluated the Staff welfare packages and performance of the Enugu Electricity Distribution Company (EEDC). In Enugu State, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives include to: ascertain the extent medical insurance affects the efficiency and the effect of retirement benefits on labour turnover of EEDC. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 780 staff was used. The adequate sample size of 264, using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error was used. 258 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed using Likert Scale and the hypotheses using Pearson correlation coefficient (r). The findings include that Medical insurance affects the efficiency of EEDC to a large extent (X value = 38.24, p value $0.0000 < 0.05$), and Retirement benefits had significant positive effect on the labour turnover of EEDC (X value = 17.75, p value $0.0000 < 0.05$). The study concluded that staff welfare packages have positive effect on performance of the EEDC. Staff welfare involves the provisions of various services, facilities and amenities for the benefit of the employees for improved standard of living. The study recommended among others that electricity transmission companies should adopt medical insurance because of the nature of their work and a healthy worker will work towards the efficiency of the organization

Keywords: Staff, Welfare, Packages, Performance, medical, allowance, Efficiency, Retirement

1.1 INTRODUCTION

In every organization, there are always people committed to working for its growth and continued sustainability. These people work towards the attainment of the organization's goals. The ability of these individuals to give their all in providing great service and making sure that resources are used efficiently determines the effectiveness of the business. In reality, a business needs a team of content and happy employees to carry out its goals, vision, and purpose (Oshagbemi, 2019). It is therefore very important for an organization to attract, retain and maintain competent and high-performance staff in its employment. The continuous care and attention given to staff

members in the form of staff welfare is likely to make them feel a sense of belonging and may affect their ability to contribute to the growth and development of the organization.

According to Ayinde (2014) and Abu (2016), staff wellbeing refers to management's attempts to make working for an organization worthwhile. The provision of numerous services, facilities, and amenities for the benefit of employees and an enhanced level of life is referred to as staff welfare. In order to increase their workforce's productivity, management of a company makes an attempt to suit their demands. In order for employees to execute their jobs well, it is important to make sure they are content and comfortable. Staff welfare has been relevant in recent times for greater achievement of desired goals of various organizations. There is the need to provide a good working environment, staff quarters or accommodation, health care services, safety and appropriate remuneration. Poor performance and low productivity may result from firms failing to sufficiently address the welfare of their employees. Some businesses now understand that focusing on employee wellbeing is one approach to practice good and efficient human resource management, which is essential to the success of a firm.

One of the essential functions of management is to determine how employees can be motivated to be highly productive by satisfying their needs. This presumption is that each employee has an internal drive that drives him in a certain way toward the accomplishment of his overall life goal. The direction of these demands or drives varies from employee to employee, according to Anikpo (2014). However, it has been simple to identify some consistent clusters of requirements, and when these needs are met, the public sector will be more productive. According to Nzelibe (2015) and Nzelibe&Moruku (2019) the assumption that Nigeria workers are motivated to perform more by increased in wages and other salary supplement such as pay leaves, fees for health care programme, bonuses, pension and gratuity plans and insurance have received some support. It is against this background that the researcher was motivated to examine staff welfare packages and performance of the Enugu Electricity Distribution Company (EEDC).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The inevitable consequences of not adopting adequate staff welfare packages on the performance of EEDC was that it could lead to inefficiency of the organization due to inadequate medical insurance. The job of the electricity distribution companies involves risk and when the men on field are not given adequate medical insurance it is likely to affect the efficiency of the organization.

Furthermore, inadequate staff welfare packages could lead to increase in labour turnover of the organization. Staff welfare package like retirement benefits is likely to make an employee to work and retire in the organization but when it is absent in an organization, it could lead to mass exodus of workers from the organization, leading to dearth of skilled workers.

Finally, inadequate staff welfare package like absence of housing allowance may affect the average cost of operation through the pilfering of the organization's properties/equipment. It is based on these anomalies that this study examined staff welfare packages and performance of the EEDC.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to examine the Staff welfare packages and performance of the EEDC. Specifically, the objectives include to:

- i. Ascertain the extent of the relationship between medical insurance and the efficiency of EEDC
- ii. Determine the relationship between retirement benefits and labour turnover of EEDC

1.4 Research Questions

- i. What is the relationship between medical insurance and the efficiency of EEDC?
- ii. What is the relationship between retirement benefit and the labour turnover of EEDC?

1.5 Statement of Hypotheses

Based on the objectives of the study and the research questions, the following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study

- i. Medical insurance has no relationship with the efficiency of EEDC
- ii. Retirement benefit has no relationship with the labour turnover of EEDC

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study will be of great benefit to the management of the electricity distribution companies, the general public, government and as future reference material on related topics.

Management of the Electricity Distribution Company: The management of the electricity distribution company will benefit from this study because through the findings of this study they will be able to understand the importance of staff welfare packages in their organization.

General Public: The general public will benefit from this study because it will lead to improvement in power generation.

Government: Government will benefit from this study because better performance of the distribution company will lead to economic development.

Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Staff Welfare

Staff welfare is any effort by the employer to make life worth living for workmen. Welfare is a broad phrase that includes a variety of services, perks, and facilities that are provided to workers by their employers as part of the substantial fringe benefits that make their lives worthwhile and inspire them to work hard. Anything done for an employee's comfort and betterment that is offered over and beyond compensation is referred to as welfare. In order to maintain an employee's services, welfare helps keep employee morale and motivation strong. Employee welfare comprises keeping an eye on working circumstances, fostering industrial harmony through the development of a health infrastructure, industrial relations, and health insurance (Abu, 2016).

2.1.2 Staff Welfare Package

The phrase "staff welfare package" refers to a wide variety of perks and services that a business may provide to its staff. Things like health insurance may be part of it. Staff wellbeing can be classified as either statutory or non-statutory, depending on whether it is demanded by the law or the management's wishes. Additional categories for welfare activities include intra-mural (conducted within the workplace) and extra-mural (conducted beyond the workplace). Facilities for employee convenience (bathrooms, drinking water), health services (first aid and treatment center, ambulance, counseling), and women and child welfare (family planning services, maternity aid) are all examples of intramural welfare. Intramural welfare facilities are those within the working environment. Extracurricular welfare activities range widely, and many of them are supported by laws passed by the government. Some of these include cozy homes, safe streets, and infrastructure, among others.

2.1.3 Medical Insurance

Health insurance is a type of insurance that covers medical expenses that arise due to an illness. These expenses could be related to hospitalization costs, cost of medicines or doctor consultation fees. Health

insurance or medical insurance is a type of insurance that covers the whole or a part of the risk of a person incurring medical expenses. As with other types of insurance, risk is shared among many individuals. By estimating the overall risk of health risk and health system expenses over the risk pool, an insurer can develop a routine finance structure, such as a monthly premium or payroll tax, to provide the money to pay for the health care benefits specified in the insurance agreement.

2.1.4 Retirement Benefits

Retirement benefits are the money or other incentives that a person collects after their employment ends. The plan to receive them is put in place while the employee is still working, and a portion of their salary, along with a contribution from the employer, is collected periodically until their retirement.

2.1.5 Efficiency

Efficiency is the (often quantifiable) capacity to prevent the wastage of resources such as time, money, energy, and materials when carrying out an action or achieving a desired outcome, according to Steiner (2018). In a broader sense, it is the capacity to carry out tasks effectively and efficiently. It is a measurement of how effectively input is utilised to carry out a job or perform a function (the output), to use more mathematical or scientific terminology. Efficiency is described as the capacity to perform an action or generate a product without wasting resources, time, or energy. This technical definition also includes the capacity to generate the intended outcome (Wilson, 2018).

2.1.6 Labour Turnover

Labour turnover has been defined as the rotation of workers around the labour market; between organizations, jobs and occupations; and between the states of employment and unemployment (Ongori 2017). Employee turnover can be voluntary or involuntary. Woods (2017), noted that each time a position is vacated, either voluntarily or involuntarily, a new employee must be hired and trained and this replacement cycle is known as labour turnover. Morrell, Loan-Clarke and Wilkinson (2019) refer to employee turnover as voluntary cessation of membership of an organization by an employee of that organization. Price (2018) indicated that employee turnover is “the entrance of new employees into the organization and the departure of existing employees from the organization”.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Expectancy Theory

This theory was proposed by Redmond in 2009. The basic idea behind the theory is that people will be motivated because they believe that their decision will lead to their desired outcome (Redmoond, 2010). Expectancy theory proposes that work motivation is performance and outcomes and individuals modify their behaviour based on their calculation of anticipated outcomes (Torrington, 2009).

This has a practical and positive benefit of improving motivation because it can, and has, helped leaders create motivational programmes in the workplace. This theory is built upon the idea that motivation comes from a person believing that he/she will get what he/she wants in the form of performance or rewards. Although the theory is not all inclusive of individual motivation factors, it provides leaders with a foundation on which to build a better theory of motivation because it emphasizes individual perceptions of the environment and subsequent interactions arising as a consequence of personal expectations.

2.2.2 Herzberg’s two-factor theory

The theory which is also referred to as the motivator – hygiene theory was propounded by Fredrick Herzberg as cited in Okorie (2012). Motivational factors are intrinsic to work itself. They make the work more challenging, enjoyable and rewarding. These factors include achievement, recognition, responsibility, advancement, growth possibility and the work itself. On the other hand, the hygiene or dissatisfiers have a preventive quality because workers may not be happy working when the environment, they operate in is not hygienic. However, the good hygiene in their work environment does not necessarily guarantee happiness. Rather, it helps to reduce the feeling of dissatisfaction. The hygiene factors explain the work context and they are established to avoid unnecessary pleasantries in workplace. The hygiene factors include; organizational policy and administration, supervision, salary, working conditions, relationship with supervisors and subordinates, status and security

2.3 Empirical Review

The empirical review is conducted based on the objectives of the study

2.3.1 Extent Medical Insurance Affects the Efficiency

In a study conducted by Poi (2020) in Bayelsa on the effect of medical insurance on the efficiency of manufacturing firms, a population of 256 workers was studied using the survey method of research and questionnaire as the major instrument of data collection. The regression method of analysis was used in the analysis and it was found that medical insurance has a significant positive effect on the efficiency of manufacturing firms.

Furthermore, Stratton (2020) conducted a study in Milan on the relationship between medical insurance and efficiency of the textile industry, in the study a population of 378 workers was studied using the survey method of research and questionnaire as the instrument of data collection, Spearman rank order correlation coefficient was used in the analysis and it was found that medical insurance has significant and positive relationship with the efficiency of the textile industry in Milan.

2.3.2 Effect of Retirement Benefits on Labour Turnover

Abu (2021) conducted a study on the effect of retirement benefits on labour turnover of civil servants in Kaduna State, in the study a population of 302 workers was studied using the survey method of research and questionnaire as the instrument of data collection. The t-test statistical tool was used in the analysis and it was found that retirement benefits have significant positive effect on labour turnover of civil servants in Kaduna State.

In a similar study conducted by Owusu-Achew (2021) in Accra Ghana on the extent retirement benefits affects the labour turnover of the civil servants in Accra, a population of 412 workers was studied using the survey method of research and questionnaire as the instrument of data collection. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to analyze the data and it was found that retirement benefit affects the labour turnover of the civil servants in Accra to a large extent.

Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted the survey descriptive research design. Survey research focuses on people and their perceptions, opinions, beliefs, attitudes, motivations and behaviour (Osuala, 2005). Survey method was adopted because the problem under study demanded the technique of questionnaire as the principal means of collecting data and survey is cost effective both for large and small population. Also, Survey was also adopted in this

research because the method was considered adequate and most appropriate in that it helped the researcher to describe, examine, record, analyze and interpret the variable that exists in the study to draw conclusions.

3.2 Area of the Study

The geographical location of the study is the various offices of EEDC in Enugu state. These offices are the regional headquarters at Okpara Avenue, the district office at Onwa plaza Awkunanaw Enugu and the service centers at Achara Layout, Agbani Road, Abakpa Nike and Emene all in Enugu state.

3.3 Sources of Data

Data for this study were obtained from the primary and secondary sources of data. The primary source adopted the questionnaire while the secondary sources of data are those sources of data, which are not the original material of the researcher. They include textbooks, journals, internet materials, seminar etc mainly from the various libraries in Enugu state.

3.4 Population of the Study

Kinnear and Taylor (1983) described population as the aggregate of all elements defined prior to the reflection of a sample. The researcher studied all the members of staff of EEDC at the regional headquarters, the district office at Onwa plaza and the various service centres in Enugu state. The breakdown of the population is as follows:

Table 3.1: Distribution of the Population

S/NO	EEDC Office	Number of workers
1	Regional Headquarters, Okpara Avenue	427
2	District Office at Onwa Plaza, Awkunanaw	164
3	All the service centers in Enugu	189
Total		780

Source: Personnel Audit, 2023.

Therefore, the population of the study is 780.

3.5 Determination of Sample Size

The random sampling technique was used to determine the sample size by using the Taro Yamane’s formula, $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$ Where n = sample size, N = population of the study, 1 = Mathematical constant, e = error limit. In this study, the population of the study is 780. The error limit is 5% i.e 0.05 Substituting in the above formula, we have

$$= \frac{780}{1+780(0.05)^2} = \frac{780}{1+780 \times 0.0025} = \frac{780}{1+1.95} = \frac{780}{2.95} = 264$$

sample size = 264

The stratified sampling was determined using the Bowley’s formula which states that

$$nh = \frac{n(Nh)}{N}$$

Where

nh = sample size for each EEDC office

Nh = Population for each EEDC office

n = Total sample size

N = Total population for all the EEDC office

Therefore, the sample size for regional headquarters, Okpara Avenue is

$$nh = \frac{264 \times 427}{780} = 144.5$$

$$= 145$$

For District office at Onwa plaza, we have

$$nh = \frac{264 \times 164}{780} = 55.50$$

$$= 55$$

For all the service centres in Enugu, we have

$$nh = \frac{264 \times 189}{780} = 63.98$$

$$= 64$$

3.6 Sampling Technique

The sampling technique adopted by the study is the simple random sampling technique. In the simple random sampling technique, the researcher randomly selected the respondents and could not influence the choice of those selected. The number selected was used as a representative of the entire population.

3.7 Instruments of Data Collection

Structured questionnaire was applied

3.8 Validity of the Instrument

Validity of the instrument, means the extent to which the research instrument measures what it is supposed to measure or accomplishes what it is supposed to accomplish. The researcher adopted expert (face) validity where the supervisor scrutinized the questionnaire items to confirm that they are related to the research questions.

3.9 Reliability of the Instrument

Reliability refers to the consistency of scores obtained by the same individuals when presented with the same test on different sets of equivalent items, or under other variable examining conditions (Ikeagwu, 1998). The researcher made use test re-tests method where 5% of the respondents were administered with the instrument and were re-administered with the instrument after two weeks interval and the reliability coefficient was found to be 0.8

3.10 Method of Data Analysis

The method of data analysis consists of inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics such as percentages, frequency tables and mean were used while the z-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Distribution and Return of Questionnaire

Table 4.1: Distribution and Return of Questionnaire

Branch	Number of Questionnaire Distributed	Number of Questionnaire Returned	Number of Questionnaire Lost	% of Valid Questionnaire
Regional H/Q EEDC	145	142	3	53.78
District office, Awk.	55	54	1	20.45
Service centres	64	62	2	23.48

Total	264	258	6	97.71
--------------	------------	------------	----------	--------------

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Table 4.1 shows that out of a total of 145 copies of questionnaire distributed to the staff members of the regional headquarters of EEDC, Enugu, 3 copies were lost, while 142 copies representing 53.78% of the total copies were returned. Out of 55 copies of questionnaire, distributed to the members of staff of EEDC, district office Awkunanaw, 1 copy was lost while 54 representing 20.45% of the total copies were returned. Out of 64 copies of questionnaire distributed to the members of staff of EEDC service centres, 2 copies were lost while 62 copies representing 23.48% of the total copies were returned. Therefore the total number of valid questionnaire was 264 copies representing 97.71% of the total copies of questionnaire distributed.

4.2 Data Relating to Research Questions

4.2.1 The extent medical insurance affects the efficiency of EEDC

Table 4.2.1: Mean rating of the extent medical insurance affects the efficiency of EEDC

Question Items	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Statistics	
						Total	Mean
The workers are efficient due to good health	129 50.00%	71 27.52%	40 15.50%	10 3.88%	8 3.10%	258	4.17
A feeling of giving more to the organization as a result of medical insurance	108 41.86%	129 50.00%	11 4.26%	6 2.33%	4 1.55%	258	4.28
A feeling of being part of the organization as a result of medical insurance	101 39.14%	113 43.79%	24 9.30%	15 5.81%	5 1.94%	258	4.12
At times, some of the family members of the worker are included which makes them to do more	111 43.02%	99 38.37%	28 10.85%	12 4.65%	8 3.10%	258	4.13
The efficiency of the organization is improved	102 39.53%	98 37.98%	29 11.24%	19 7.36%	10 3.88	258	4.02

Cluster Mean	42.71%	39.53%	10.23%	4.80	2.71	4.14

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.2.1 shows that 129 respondents strongly agree that the workers are efficient due to good health, 71 respondents agree, 40 respondents were undecided, 10 respondents disagree while 8 respondents strongly disagree.

Table 4.2.1 depicts that 108 respondents strongly agree that the organization is efficient there is a feeling of giving more to the organization as a result of medical insurance, 108 respondents agree, 11 respondents were undecided, 6 respondents disagree while 4 respondents strongly disagree.

Table 4.2.1 shows that 101 respondents strongly agree a feeling of being part of the organization as a result of medical insurance, 113 respondents agree, 24 respondents were undecided, 15 respondents disagree while 5 respondents strongly disagree.

Table 4.2.1 shows that 111 respondents strongly agree that at times, some of the family members of the worker are included in the medical insurance which makes them to do more, 99 respondents agree, 28 respondents were undecided, 12 respondents disagree while 10 respondents strongly disagree.

Table 4.2.1 shows that 102 respondents strongly agree that the efficiency of the organization is improved, 98 respondents agree, 29 respondents were undecided, 19 respondents agree while 10 respondents strongly disagree.

4.2.2 Effect of retirement benefit on the labour turnover of EEDC

Question items	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Statistics	
						Total	Mean
The worker retires with the organization because of the benefit	104 40.31%	97 37.60%	38 14.73%	10 3.88%	9 3.49%	258	4.07
There is a reduction in labour turnover	99 38.72%	98 37.98%	31 12.02%	16 6.20%	14 3.43%	258	3.97
Rest of mind for retirement	121 46.90%	85 32.95%	19 7.36%	20 7.75%	13 5.04%	4258	4.09
The worker is motivated due to the retirement benefits	106 41.09%	112 43.41%	25 9.69%	8 8.10%	7 2.71%	258	4.17
The worker concentrates in the work due to the retirement benefit	116 44.96%	101 39.15%	22 8.53%	10 3.88%	14 4%		

						258	4.20
Cluster Mean	42.00%	39.00%	14.25%	19.00%	17.25%		4.10

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.2.2 shows that 104 respondents strongly agree that the worker retires with the organization because of the benefit, 97 respondents agree, 38 respondents were undecided, 10 respondents disagree while 9 respondents strongly disagree.

Table 4.2.2 depicts that 99 respondents strongly agree that there is a reduction in labour turnover, 98 respondents agree, 31 respondents were undecided, 16 respondents disagree while 4 respondents strongly disagree.

Table 4.2.2 shows that 121 respondents strongly agree that the effect is rest of mind for retirement, 85 respondents agree, 19 respondents were undecided, 20 respondents disagree while 13 respondents strongly disagree.

Table 4.2.2 shows that 106 respondents strongly agree that the worker is motivated due to the retirement benefits, 112 respondents agree, 25 respondents were undecided, 8 respondents disagree while 7 respondents strongly disagree.

Table 4.2.2 shows that 116 respondents strongly agree that the worker concentrates in the work due to the retirement benefit, 101 respondents agree, 22 respondents were undecided, 10 respondents agree while 14 respondents strongly disagree.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

4.3.2 Test of hypothesis One

H₀₁: Medical insurance does not affect the efficiency of EEDC to a large extent

Table 4.3.1: Contingency table for testing of Hypothesis One

Question Items	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Statistics	
						Mean	Std.
The workers are efficient due to good health	129 50.00%	71 27.52%	40 15.50%	10 3.88%	8 3.10%	4.17	1.21
A feeling of giving more to the organization as a result of medical insurance	108 41.86%	129 50.00%	11 4.26%	6 2.33%	4 1.55%	4.28	1.35
A feeling of being part of the organization as a result of medical insurance	101 39.14%	113 43.79%	24 9.30%	15 5.81%	5 1.94%	4.12	1.28
At times, some of the family members of the worker are included which makes them to do more	111 43.02%	99 38.37%	28 10.85%	12 4.65%	8 3.10%	4.13	1.21
						4.02	1.17

The efficiency of the organization is improved	102	98	29	19	10		
	39.53%	37.98%	11.24%	7.36%	3.88		
Cluster Mean	42.71%	39.53%	10.23%	4.80	2.71	4.14	1.24

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The cluster mean of 4.14 > 3.00 (Likert mean) and associated standard deviation of 1.24 < 1.581 (Likert standard deviation) indicates that the out listed are effects of medical insurance on the efficiency of EEDC

Level of Significance (α) = 0.05

Test statistic: One-sample $t = \frac{\bar{x} - \mu_0}{\frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}} = 38.24$

Decision rule: Reject H_0 if p-value ≤ 0.05 , otherwise do not reject. OR reject H_0 if the calculated value > the critical table value, otherwise, do not reject.

P-value = 0.0000

Interpretation: The one-sample t-test result with t-statistic value of 38.24 and associated probability value of 0.0000 < 0.05 shows that medical insurance affects the efficiency of EEDC to a large extent.

Decision for Hypothesis One

The paper therefore rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternate hypothesis which states that medical insurance affects the efficiency of EEDC to a large extent.

4.3.2 Test of hypothesis two

H_{01} : Retirement benefit does not significantly affect the labour turnover of EEDC

Table 4.3.2: Contingency table for testing of Hypothesis Two

Question items	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Statistics	
						Mean	Std.
The worker retires with the organization because of the benefit	104 40.31%	97 37.60%	38 14.73%	10 3.88%	9 3.49%	4.07	0.96
There is a reduction in labour turnover	99 38.72%	98 37.98%	31 12.02%	16 6.20%	14 3.43%	3.97	0.99
Rest of mind for retirement	121 46.90%	85 32.95%	19 7.36%	20 7.75%	13 5.04%	4.09	1.21
The worker is motivated due to the retirement benefits	106 41.09%	112 43.41%	25 9.69%	8 8.10%	7 2.71%	4.17	1.22

The worker concentrates in the work due to the retirement benefit	116 44.96%	101 39.15%	22 8.53%	10 3.88%	14 4%		
Cluster Mean	42.00%	39.00%	14.25%	19.00%	17.25%	4.10	1.09

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The cluster mean of 4.10 > 3.00 (Likert mean) and associated standard deviation of 1.09 < 1.581 (Likert standard deviation) indicates that the out listed are effects retirement benefits on the labour turnover of EEDC

Level of Significance (α) = 0.05

Test statistic: One-sample $t = \frac{\bar{x} - \mu_0}{\frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}} = 17.75$

Decision rule: Reject H_0 if p-value ≤ 0.05 , otherwise do not reject. OR reject H_0 If the calculated value > the critical table value, otherwise, do not reject.

P-value = 0.0000

Interpretation: The one-sample t-test result with t-statistic value of 17.75 and associated probability value of 0.0000 < 0.05 shows that retirement benefits have significant positive effect on the labour turnover of EEDC

Decision for Hypothesis Two

The paper therefore rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternate hypothesis which states that retirement benefits have significant positive effect on the labour turnover of EEDC.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

4.3.1 Medical insurance affects the efficiency of EEDC to a large extent.

Medical insurance affects the efficiency of EEDC to a large extent. The evidence is shown in the (X value = 38.24, p value 0.0000 < 0.05). In the empirical review conducted by Poi (2020) on the effect of medical insurance on the efficiency of manufacturing firms, although both studies were conducted using different analytical method and different locations, it was found that medical insurance affects the efficiency of EEDC to a large extent

4.3.2 Retirement benefits have significant positive effect on the labour turnover

Retirement benefits have significant positive effect on the labour turnover of EEDC. The evidence is shown in the (X value = 17.75, p value 0.0000 < 0.05). In the empirical review conducted by Abu (2021) on the effect of retirement benefit on the labour turnover of civil service and it was discovered that retirement benefits have significant positive effect on the labour turnover of EEDC.

5.1 Summary of Findings

1. Medical insurance affects the efficiency of EEDC to a large extent (X value = 38.24, p value 0.0000 < 0.05).
2. Retirement benefits have significant positive effect on the labour turnover of EEDC (X value = 17.75, p value 0.0000 < 0.05).

5.2 Conclusion

This paper concludes that staff welfare packages have positive effect on performance of the EEDC. Staff welfare involves the provisions of various services, facilities and amenities for the benefit of the employees for improved standard of living. It is part of the efforts of management of an organization to meet the needs of their workforce

in order to improve their productive capacity. Staff welfare is directed towards ensuring that the employees are happy and comfortable, in order to perform their tasks effectively. Staff welfare has been relevant in recent times for greater achievement of desired goals of various organizations

5.3 Recommendations

The paper recommends that electricity transmission companies should

1. Adopt medical insurance because of the nature of their work and a healthy worker will work towards the efficiency of the organization
2. Integrate retirement benefit as that welfare package can reduce labour turnover

References

- Abu, M.M. (2016). The role of well structure welfare package on the daily output of construction workers in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 1(2), 302-401.
- Aderinto, A. (2018). Improving labour productivity in the service sector in Nigeria: The before labour and management, perman. *Journal of the Institute of Personal Management of Nigeria*, 8(2), 17–38.
- Akintunde, A.D. (2018). *How to motivate workers to achieve higher productivity*. Oyo State: Unpublished Business Studies Polytechnic Ibadan; 2005.
- Aldaibat, B.F. &Irtaimh, H. (2019). The role of strategic human resource management at Jordanian Banking Sector through implementation total quality management (TQM). *European Scientific Journal*, 8(25), 45-56.
- Anyadike, N.O. (2019). Human resource planning and employee productivity in Nigeria public organization. *Global Journal of Human Resource Management*, 1(4), 56-68.
- Armstrong, M.A. (2018). *Handbook on personnel management practice*. London: Kogan Page Ltd.
- Chandler, A.D. (2018). *Strategy and structure*. Cambridge: MIT Press.
- Chinwoh, K. (2019). Fringe benefits: Are you aware of all you are entitled to? *Management in Nigeria*, 25(2), 201-219.
- Dixit, V. and Bhati, M. (2018). A study about employee commitment and its impact on sustained productivity in Indian Auto-Component Industry. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 1(6), 34 – 51.
- Ede, T.E & Mbah, P.C. (2020) Evaluation of the relationship between organizational Compensation and employee output in five selected manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. *Saudi journal of Humanities and social Sciences* 8(5), 2347-9493
- Ejiofor, P.O. (2018). Employee welfare programmes: Dilemmas during depression. in U.G. Damachi and T. Fashoyin (eds), *Contemporary problems in Nigeria industrial relations*. Lagos: Development Press Ltd.
- Ejiogu, A. (2019). *Human resource management towards greater productivity*. Lagos: Generation Press Ltd.

- Etzioni, A. (2019). Two approaches to organizational analysis: A critique and a suggestion. *Administrative science quarterly*, 5(2), 257-278.
- Ezeh, C. (2018). *Human resource management; issue, development and utilization*. Nigeria: Rex Charles and Patrick Ltd.
- Francis, A.C. (2019). The role of human resource planning in recruitment and selection process. *British Journal of Humanity and Social Sciences*, 6(2), 69-77.
- Freedom Learning Group (2019). Available at <https://courses.lumenlearning.com/wmopen-organizationalbehavior/chapter/theories-of-motivation/>. Retrieved on 2nd December, 2021.
- Gong, Y., Law, K. S., Chang, S., & Xin, K. R. (2019). Human resources management and firm performance: The differential role of managerial affective and continuance commitment. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 94, 263-275.
- Hui, H. (2022). Influence of Organizational Learning and Innovation on Organizational Performance in Asian Manufacturing Food Industry. *Asian Journal of Empirical Research*, 3(8),962-971.
- Hui, H. (2022). The Impact of Firm Age and Size on the Relationship Among Organizational Innovation, Learning, and Performance: A Moderation Analysis in Asian Food Manufacturing Companies. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 5(3), 842-851.
- Mbah, P. C., Ekechukwu, C., &Chukwudi, G. F., (2018). Effectiveness of staff motivation strategies in manufacturing companies in Enugu state. *International Journal of Business Economics and Management Research*, 9(6), 1-2.
- Odeku, K.O. and Odeku, O.F. (2018). In pursuit of the employees' welfare in the workplace: Issues in perspectives. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(15), 24-38.
- Ofobruku, S. A. &Iheabunike, O. B. C. (2018). Assessment of Recruitment Practice on Organisation Performance: Empirical Study of Hospitality Businesses in Abuja. *European Scientific Journal*, 9(29), 1857–7881.
- Okumbe, J.A. (2021). *Human resource management*. Nairobi: Accts Press.
- Oyewobi, L.O. (2018). Influence of public service motivation on job satisfaction and organizational commitment of Quantity Surveyors in Nigerian Public Service. *Social and Management Research Journal*, 10(1), 29-42.
- Richard, P.J., Devinney, T.M., Yip, G.S., Johnson, G. (2019). Measuring organizational performance: Towards methodological best practice. *Journal of Management*. SAGE Publications, 35(3), 718–804.

Robbins, S.P. (2021). *Organizational behaviour.12th edition*. New Jersey: Pearson Education, Incorporated.

Stephen, G.C.&Muathe, S.M.A. (2022). A critical review of literature on performance contracting. *Global Journal on Commerce and Management Perspectives*,3(6), 65-70.